

Some interesting species of *Hymenoscyphus* from Greece

Panagiotis Delivorias*, Ioannis Dimitriadis, Zacharoula Gonou-Zagou & Evangelia Kapsanaki-Gotsi

University of Athens, Faculty of Biology, Department of Ecology and Systematics, GR–15784 Athens, Greece

Received 20 January 2010 / Accepted 14 July 2010

Abstract. Four interesting species of the genus *Hymenoscyphus* are presented from Greece. *Hymenoscyphus serotinus* is newly reported from Greece, whereas *H. scutululus* and *H. virgultorum* are reported for the second time. The formation of chlamydospores was observed in apothecia of *H. scutululus*. Descriptions, line drawings and microscopic photographs of all studied taxa are presented.

Key words: *Ascomycota*, cup fungi, discomycetes, taxonomy

Introduction

The genus *Hymenoscyphus* is placed in the family *Helotiaceae* and comprises about 155 species worldwide (Kirk *et al.* 2008). In general, members of the genus produce small-sized, often minute, sessile to stipitate, whitish to yellow apothecia with 8-spored asci that open by an amyloid apical pore. The paraphyses are filiform to cylindrical, mostly straight, and the ascospores are ellipsoid to fusiform or slightly inequilateral, hyaline and inamyloid (Dennis 1978; Lizoň 1992; Vesterholt 2000).

The circumscription of the genus is not well-defined and as yet few phylogenetic studies involving members of *Hymenoscyphus* have been performed (Egger & Sigler 1993; Gernandt *et al.* 2001; Zhang & Zhuang 2004; Wang *et al.* 2006). As a result, the relationships between species of *Hymenoscyphus* and other genera of the *Helotiaceae* are not clear. Recent studies have suggested the accommodation of certain members of *Hymenoscyphus* in other genera, transferring *Hymenoscyphus ericae* (D.J. Read) Korf & Kernan and related species to the newly proposed genus *Rhizoscyphus* (Zhang & Zhuang 2004), and the group of species surrounding *H. epiphyllus* (Pers.) Rehm ex Kauffman to *Phaeobelotium* (Hengstmengel 2009).

To date, four members of the genus have been reported from Greece, namely *H. fructigenus*, *H. scutululus*, *H. vernus* (Boud.) Dennis and *H. virgultorum*, the latter three only once (Zervakis *et al.* 1999; Perlerou & Diamandis 2000). However,

this is probably a misrepresentation, as the small size of the apothecia has no doubt led to their being overlooked in various forays. In this study four species are presented: *H. fructigenus*, *H. scutululus*, *H. serotinus* and *H. virgultorum*. *H. serotinus* is reported for the first time from Greece, *H. scutululus* and *H. virgultorum* for the second time.

Materials and methods

Microscopic observations were made using a Zeiss Axioimager Differential Interference Contrast (DIC) microscope. Initially, Melzer's reagent was used for observation, measurements and photography, and sections of the dried material were pretreated with 3% KOH solution in order for the amyloid reaction of the apical apparatus of the asci to be observed. After the important work of Baral (1987, 2009) on hemiamyloidity was brought to our attention, sections were also mounted in Lugol's solution, both with and without prior treatment with KOH, to ascertain whether the reaction is actually hemiamyloid. All measurements were performed under 1000× magnification. Only spores released from the asci were measured. Spore sizes are given in approximation to 0.1 µm, with extreme values given in parentheses, followed by the length-width ratio of the spores (Q). Habitat references in the descriptions refer exclusively to the material collected for the present study. Greek localities are transliterated to Latin according to ISO 843: 1997 (E). Authorities' abbrevi-

*Corresponding author: e-mail: panadeli@biol.uoa.gr

ations are in accordance with Kirk & Ansell (1992). All collected specimens are deposited at the Mycological Herbarium of the University of Athens (ATHU–M).

Descriptions

Hymenoscyphus fructigenus (Bull.) Gray, Nat. Arr. Brit. Pl. 1: 673 (1821).

Apothecia 0.5–1.5 mm, minute, disk-shaped; upper surface plane, whitish, cream to ochre when fresh, pale yellow on drying, glabrous; outer surface whitish, glabrous to minutely downy (Fig. 3h). **Stalk** 0.5–4 × 0.1–0.5 mm, rudimentary to conspicuous, in some specimens markedly long, filiform, subconcolorous to the disk.

Ascospores (12.5–) 13.5–17.0 × 3.5–4.5 (–5.0) µm, Q=3.38–4.08, fusiform-ellipsoid, somewhat inequilateral, smooth, hyaline, aseptate or 1-septate, rarely 2-septate (Figs 1, 3a). **Asci** 85–140 × 7–10 µm, 8-spored, clavate-cylindrical, bluntly conical at the apex, tapering towards the base; apical pore hemiamyloid, in Lugol's solution staining reddish brown prior to KOH and blue after KOH, in Melzer's reagent negative to faintly bluish prior to KOH and blue after KOH (Figs 3d–g). **Paraphyses** up to 3 µm wide, filiform, hyaline, some with golden-yellow granular content; apices obtuse, straight to slightly bent (Fig. 3b). **Ectal excipulum** of textura porrecta to textura prismatica, composed of thick-walled cells 18–34 × 4–12 (–23) µm; wall up to 1.2 µm thick (Fig. 3c). **Medullary excipulum** of textura intricata, composed of thin-walled, interwoven hyphae 2–7 µm wide.

Fig. 1. Ascospores of *H. fructigenus*. Scale bar = 10 µm

Habitat: gregarious on acorns and cupules of *Quercus* and *Juglans*.

Collections examined: GREECE: **ATTIKI**, Mt. Ymittos, Cholargos, on cupules and acorns of *Quercus coccifera*, 3 Dec 2000, Dimitriadis (ATHU–M 4611); **KARDITSA**, lake Plastira, alt. ca 800 m, forest of *Quercus frainetto*, on acorns of *Q. frainetto*, 30 Sep 2009, Delivorias & Dimitriadis (ATHU–M 6299); **FTHIOTIDA**, Mt. Oiti, Kastania, on a cupule of *Juglans regia*, 7 Nov 2009, Delivorias (ATHU–M 6345).

Remarks: The habitat of *H. fructigenus* is distinctive, and, in combination with the fusiform, frequently septate spores, makes identification quite safe. The substrates include pericarps, acorns and nuts of broad-leaved trees, as well as cones of conifers (Lizoň 1992).

This species is quite variable. The colour of the disk as reported in the literature ranges from white or nearly so (Jordan 1995: white; Breitenbach & Kränzlin 1984: whitish to ochre-whitish; Vesterholt 2000: white to yellowish), to clearly yellow (Dennis 1978: yellowish; Lizoň 1992: yellow to yellow-ochraceous; Moser 1963: golden yellow). This variation in colour was present in our specimens, with the colour of the disk ranging from white to ochre-yellow even within the same collection. The length of the stipe also varied significantly, ranging from rudimentary to markedly long. Paraphyses with a golden-yellow granular content were observed in the more brighter-coloured apothecia but were more or less absent in the pale-coloured ones. Finally, the structure of the ectal excipulum ranged from a typical textura porrecta of rather narrow cells, as mentioned by Lizoň (1992), to, in one specimen, a textura prismatica of short and broad cells (Fig. 3c). It is possible that some infraspecific taxa are involved. Apart from the typical variety, two further varieties are recognized by Hengstmengel (1985), who erected *H. fructigenus* var. *carpini* (Batsch) Hengstmengel to accommodate *Peziza carpini* Batsch, and *H. fructigenus* var. *coryli* (Feuill.) Hengstmengel to accommodate *Helotium fructigenum* forma *coryli* Feuill. Further studies are needed on this issue.

According to Lizoň (1992), *H. fructigenus* should be placed in the group of *H. serotinus*, where it would come close to *H. virgultorum*. However, recent molecular data (Zhang & Zhuang 2004) show that *H. fructigenus* is more closely related to species such as *H. scutulus* and *H. caudatus* (P. Karst.) Dennis, and that *H. serotinus* joins the above group with certain differences in sequence composition.

In Greece, *H. fructigenus* has been previously reported from the island of Andros, on *Quercus ilex*, *Q. coccifera* and *Quercus* sp., and from Mt. Ossa, on *Fagus sylvatica* (Zervakis *et al.* 1999).

Hymenoscyphus scutulus (Pers.) W. Phillips, Man. Brit. Discomyc.: 136, 1887 [as '*Hymenoscypha scutula*'].

Apothecia 0.5–1.5 mm, minute, disk-shaped; upper surface plane, cream to pale yellow, glabrous; outer surface whitish, minutely downy (Fig. 3t). **Stalk** distinct, markedly long, filiform, subconcolorous to the disk.

Ascospores 21.0–25.0 × 4.0–5.2 µm, Q=4.20–5.56, fusiform-ellipsoid, smooth, hyaline, aseptate, with cilia usually on both ends, less often only on one end (Figs 2, 3i–k). **Asci** 100–130 × 7–9 µm, 8-spored, clavate-cylindrical, bluntly conical at the apex, tapering towards the base; apical pore hemiamyloid, in Lugol's solution staining reddish brown prior to KOH and blue after KOH, in Melzer's reagent faintly blue prior to KOH and blue after KOH (Figs 3l–o). **Paraphyses** up to 3 µm wide, filiform, hyaline; apices obtuse, straight. **Ectal excipulum** of textura porrecta, composed of parallel cells 10–22 × 6–9 µm, with somewhat thickened walls. **Medullary excipulum** of textura porrecta, composed of thin-walled, parallel hyphae 2–5 µm wide (Fig. 3p). **Chlamydospores** originating from the hyphae of the medullary excipulum, intercalary or terminal, 10–16 × 5.6–

Fig. 3: a–h. *H. fructigenus*: a. Ascospores; b. Paraphyses; c. Hyphae of the ectal excipulum; d–g. Apical apparatus treated with Lugol's solution (d. prior to KOH, e. after KOH) and Melzer's reagent (f. prior to KOH, g. after KOH); h. Apothecia on an acorn of *Quercus coccifera*, 3× life size; i–t. *H. scutulus*: i–k. Ascospores with ciliae (arrows); l–o. Apical apparatus treated with Lugol's solution (l. prior to KOH, m. after KOH) and Melzer's reagent (n. prior to KOH, o. after KOH); p. Intercalary chlamydospore originating from a hypha of the medullary excipulum; q. Free intercalary chlamydospore; r. Free terminal chlamydospore; s. Germinating chlamydospore; t. Dried apothecia on a herbaceous stem, 3× life size (arrows). Scale bars = 10 µm

Fig. 2. Ascospores of *H. scutululus*. Scale bar = 10 μ m

8.3 μ m, subglobose, ovoid to pyriform, hyaline in KOH, yellowish in Melzer's reagent, dark orange-brown in Lugol's solution; wall up to 1 μ m thick (Fig. 3p–s).

Habitat: gregarious on a dead herbaceous stem, in a forest of *Castanea sativa*.

Collection examined: GREECE: KARDITSA, lake Plastira, alt. ca 950 m, Neraida, forest of *Castanea sativa*, on a dead herbaceous stem, 14 Nov 1999, Delivorias (ATHU–M 5852).

Remarks: This is a remarkable species on account of its fusiform spores with cilia on one or both ends. This feature is shared by *H. scutuloides* Hengstm., which has narrower spores with 1–3 (–4) ciliae at each end and asci that originate from croziers (Hengstmengler 1996).

To our surprise, in one preparation chlamydospores were observed originating from hyphae of the medullary excipulum and detaching upon maturity. A number of liberated, germinating spores were also seen floating in the preparation. No such spores were observed in two other sections made from a different ascocarp of the same collection. The formation of chlamydospores on apothecia is a remarkable feature. To our knowledge, it has not been previously reported.

This is the second report of *H. scutululus* from Greece. It has been previously reported from the island of Andros (Zervakis *et al.* 1999).

Hymenoscyphus serotinus (Pers.) W. Phillips, Man. Brit. Discomyc.: 125, 1887 [as '*Hymenoscypha serotina*'].

Misapplied name: *H. calyculus* (Sowerby : Fr.) W. Phillips, sensu Breitenbach & Kränzlin (1984).

Apothecia 0.5–6.0 mm, disk-shaped; upper surface plane, ochre-yellow to yolk-yellow when fresh, orange-yellow on drying, glabrous; outer surface whitish to cream, minutely downy (Fig. 4l). **Stalk** distinct, long, subconcolorous to the disk.

Ascospores (18.0–) 21.0–26.0 (–29.0) \times 2.9–3.5 (–4.0) μ m, Q=5.15–8.79, clavate, inequilateral, occasionally curved, smooth, hyaline, aseptate or rarely with a single septum, particularly in germinating spores (Figs 4a–f, 5). **Asci** 100–140 \times 8–10 μ m, 8-spered, clavate-cylindrical, bluntly conical at

Fig. 5. Ascospores of *H. serotinus*. Scale bar = 10 μ m

the apex, tapering below; apical pore hemiamyloid, in Lugol's solution staining reddish brown prior to KOH and blue after KOH, in Melzer's reagent faintly blue prior to KOH and blue after KOH (Figs 4g–j). **Paraphyses** up to 3 μ m wide, filiform, hyaline. **Ectal excipulum** of textura porrecta, composed of somewhat thick-walled cells 11–23 \times 4.5–7 μ m wide (Fig. 4k). **Medullary excipulum** of textura porrecta, composed of thin-walled hyphae 2–4 μ m wide.

Habitat: gregarious on twigs and branches of *Fagus sylvatica*.

Collections examined: GREECE: KARDITSA, Mt. Zygourolivado, alt. ca 1550 m, forest of *Fagus sylvatica*, on twigs and branches of *F. sylvatica*, 14 Nov 1999, Delivorias (ATHU–M 5854, 5855, 5856); 15 Oct 2000, Delivorias (ATHU–M 5857, 5858); 29 Oct 2000, Delivorias (ATHU–M 5859); 10 Nov 2002, Delivorias (ATHU–M 5860); 10 Oct 2009, Delivorias & Bonetti (ATHU–M 6304, 6305).

Remarks: This species is similar macroscopically to *H. virgultorum*, but the long, clavate, inequilateral spores are quite distinctive. Breitenbach & Kränzlin (1984) provide a description and an illustration of this species under the name *H. calyculus*. We agree with Lizoň (1992) that *H. serotinus* is a distinct species, despite its affinity to *H. virgultorum*, as its spores are not only consistently larger but also significantly narrower, resulting in an overall different shape with a much greater Q ratio.

H. serotinus is hereby newly reported from Greece. It was collected on five different occasions from the same beech forest, where it was very common. Given its abundance in the particular study area, it is quite possible that its distribution in Greece is much wider, and that it has been overlooked due to its small size. *H. virgultorum* was also collected from the same beech forest, albeit only once.

Hymenoscyphus virgultorum (Vahl.) W. Phillips, Man. Brit. Discomyc.: 134, 1887 [as '*Hymenoscypha virgultorum*'].

= *H. conscriptus* (P. Karst.) Korf.

Misapplied name: *H. calyculus* (Sowerby : Fr.) W. Phillips.

Apothecia 0.5–2.5 mm, disk-shaped; upper surface plane, ochre-yellow to yolk-yellow when fresh, orange to orange-brown on drying, glabrous; outer surface whitish to cream, minutely downy (Fig. 4z). **Stalk** distinct, long, subconcolorous to the disk.

Fig. 4: a–l. *H. serotinus*: a–d. Ascospores; e–f. Germinating ascospores with septum (arrow); g–j. Apical apparatus treated with Lugol's solution (g. prior to KOH, h. after KOH) and Melzer's reagent (i. prior to KOH, j. after KOH); k. Hyphae of the ectal excipulum; l. Apothecia on branches of *Fagus sylvatica*, 3× life size (photo: A. Bonetti); m–z. *H. virgultorum*: m–q. Ascospores; r–s. Germinating ascospores with septum (arrow); t–x. Apical apparatus treated with Lugol's solution (t. prior to KOH, u. after KOH) and Melzer's reagent (v. prior to KOH, x. after KOH); y. Hyphae of the ectal excipulum; z. Dried apothecia on bark of *Fagus sylvatica*, 3× life size (arrows). Scale bars = 10 μm

Fig. 6. Ascospores of *H. virgultorum*. Scale bar = 10 μ m

Ascospores 13.5–16.3 \times 4.0–5.0 μ m, $Q=3.25$ –3.89, fusiform-ellipsoid, inequilateral, smooth, hyaline, aseptate or occasionally 1-septate (Figs 4m–s, 6). **Asci** 110–130 \times 7–10 μ m, 8-spored, clavate-cylindrical, bluntly conical at the apex, tapering towards the base; apical pore hemiamyloid, in Lugol's solution staining reddish brown prior to KOH and blue after KOH, in Melzer's reagent faintly blue prior to KOH and blue after KOH (Figs 4t–x). **Paraphyses** up to 3 μ m wide, filiform, hyaline; apices obtuse, equal to somewhat broadened, straight. **Ectal excipulum** of textura porrecta, composed of thick-walled cells 16–35 \times 6–9.5 μ m wide (Fig. 4y). **Medullary excipulum** of textura porrecta, composed of thin-walled, parallel hyphae 3–6 μ m broad.

Habitat: gregarious on bark of *Fagus sylvatica*.

Collection examined: GREECE: KARDITSA, Mt. Zygourolivado, alt. ca 1550 m, forest of *Fagus sylvatica*, on bark of *F. sylvatica*, 8 Sep 2002, Delivorias (ATHU–M 5853).

Remarks: Dennis (1960, 1978) characterizes *H. virgultorum* as an ill-defined name, and instead prefers *H. calyculus*, a view that is also currently adopted by *Index Fungorum*. However, Lizoň (1992) notes that the correct name for this taxon should in fact be *H. virgultorum*, on the grounds that *Peziza virgultorum* Oeder is the earliest validly published name for the taxon, and that the holotype of *Peziza calyculus* Sowerby represents a member of *Sclerotiniaceae*.

H. virgultorum and *H. serotinus* are almost indistinguishable in the field, but their spores are quite different. A similar-looking species with a different habitat is *H. fructigenus*, which produces somewhat narrower, frequently septate spores in contrast to the mostly aseptate spores of *H. virgultorum*.

H. virgultorum has been reported from Greece only once in the past, from a beech forest at Mt. Oxya, Fthiotida. The find was originally published by Zervakis *et al.* (1999) and later presented in more detail by Dimou *et al.* (2002). Although it had been unreported at the time, the authors stated that the species is 'relatively common', presumably in their study area. We have collected *H. virgultorum* once, this collection being the second report of the species from Greece.

Acknowledgements. We wish to thank the anonymous reviewer who brought to our attention the usefulness of Lugol's solution in the study of ascomycetes. Thanks are also due to wildlife photographer Andrea Bonetti for kindly permitting us to use the photograph of *H. serotinus* which he took during a field trip with the corresponding author.

References

- Baral, H.O. 1987. Lugol's solution/IKI versus Melzer's reagent: Hemiamyloidity, a universal feature of the ascus wall. — *Mycotaxon* 29: 399–450.
- Baral, H.O. 2009. Iodine reaction in *Ascomycetes*: why is Lugol's solution superior to Melzer's reagent? <http://www.gbif-mycology.de/HostedSites/Baral/IodineReaction.htm>
- Breitenbach, J. & Kränzlin, F. 1984. Fungi of Switzerland. Vol. 1. *Ascomycetes*. Edition Mykologia, Lucerne.
- Dennis, R.W.G. 1960. British cup fungi and their allies. Quaritch, London.
- Dennis, R.W.G. 1978. British *Ascomycetes*. J. Cramer, Vaduz.
- Dimou, D.M., Zervakis, G.I. & Polemis, E. 2002. Mycodiversity studies in selected ecosystems of Greece: I. Macrofungi from the southernmost *Fagus* forest in the Balkans (Oxya Mountain, Central Greece). — *Mycotaxon* 82: 177–205.
- Egger, K.N. & Sigler, L. 1993. Relatedness of the ericoid endophytes *Scytalidium vaccinii* and *Hymenoscyphus ericae* inferred from analysis of ribosomal DNA. — *Mycologia* 85: 219–230.
- Gernandt, D.S., Platt, J.L., Stone, J.K., Spatafora, J.W., Holst-Jensen, A., Hamelin, R.C. & Kohn, L.M. 2001. Phylogenetics of *Helotiales* and *Rhytismatales* based on partial small subunit nuclear ribosomal DNA sequences. — *Mycologia* 93: 915–933.
- Hengstmengel, J. 1985. Notes on *Hymenoscyphus*. — *Persoonia* 12: 489–490.
- Hengstmengel, J. 1996. Notes on *Hymenoscyphus* II. On three non-fructicolous species of the 'fructigenus-group' with croziers. — *Persoonia* 16: 191–207.
- Hengstmengel, J. 2009. Notes on *Hymenoscyphus* 3. On the nomenclature of *Hymenoscyphus subcarneus* (*Ascomycota*, *Helotiales*). — *Mycotaxon* 107: 267–276.
- ISO 843:1997 (E). Information and documentation – Conversion of Greek characters into Latin characters. International Organization for Standardization.
- Jordan, M. 1995. The Encyclopedia of Fungi of Britain and Europe. David & Charles, Devon.
- Kirk, P.M. & Ansell, A.E. 1992. Authors of fungal names. Index of Fungi supplement. CAB International, Wallingford.
- Kirk, P.M., Cannon, P.F., Minter, D.W. & Stalpers, J.A. 2008. Dictionary of the fungi. 10th edn. CABI Europe, UK.
- Lizoň, P. 1992. The genus *Hymenoscyphus* (*Helotiales*) in Slovakia, Czechoslovakia. — *Mycotaxon* 45: 1–59.
- Moser, M. 1963. *Ascomyceten*. — In: H. Gams [ed.]. *Kleine Kryptogamenflora Band IIa*. Gustav Fischer Verlag, Stuttgart.
- Perlerou, C. & Diamandis, S. 2000. [New records of macrofungi in Greece]. — *Dasiki Erevna* 13: 51–57. (In Greek)
- Vesterholt, J. 2000. *Hymenoscyphus* Gray. — In: L. Hansen & H. Knudsen [eds]. *Nordic Macromycetes*. Vol. 1. *Ascomycetes*. Nordsvamp, Copenhagen.
- Wang, Z., Binder, M., Schoch, C.L., Johnston, P.R., Spatafora, J.W. & Hibbett, D.S. 2006. Evolution of helotialean fungi (*Leotiomyces*, *Pezizomycotina*): A nuclear rDNA phylogeny. — *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 41: 295–312.
- Zervakis, G., Lizoň, P., Dimou, D. & Polemis, E. 1999. Annotated check-list of the Greek macrofungi II. *Ascomycotina*. — *Mycotaxon* 72: 487–506.
- Zhang, Y-H. & Zhuang, W-Y. 2004. Phylogenetic relationships of some members in the genus *Hymenoscyphus* (*Ascomycetes*, *Helotiales*). — *Nova Hedwigia* 78: 475–484.